

Factors Influencing the Optimization of Organizational Sustainable Performance

Author's Details: Rajendran Muthuveloo, Dominic Santanasamy, Teoh Ai Ping
Graduate School of Business, University Sains Malaysia, 11800 USM, Penang, Malaysia

Abstract

This research was carried out to identify the factors which influence the organizational sustainable performance. A total of 150 sets of structures questionnaires were distributed to the Multinational Corporations (MNCs) located in Malaysia and 84.6 percent of the total questionnaires sent were responded and returned. In order to test the relationship between the variables, the data collected from the respondents were analysed using various statistical techniques including descriptive statistics, factor analysis, reliability analysis, correlation analysis and regression analysis. The results show that Technology and Organizational Type has significant influence on optimization of organizational sustainable performance. In an increasingly competitive global market, more and more organization is striving for optimizing their performance. The finding in this study resulted in recommending the management on factors which influence the organization performance and thus helps in the formation of strategies to enhance the factors for optimizing and sustaining the performance. This study contributes to the limited empirical research examining the effectiveness of the factors introduced to which organizational sustainable performances are achieved. In addition the study provides an empirical analysis of the association between the five factors introduced (Income, Technology, Organization Type, People and Quality). The research described in this study provides evidence that paying equal attention to both Income and Technology Type factors is paramount in order to create a successful performance-driven organization that could achieve sustainable organizational performance.

Keywords: Organizational Sustainable Performance, Income, Technology, Organization Type, People, Quality.

1.0 Introduction

Achieving organization success and sustaining the performance is always the prime target of all organization. To survive in today's rapidly changing environment, organizations must identify their existing positions, clarify their goals and operate more effectively and efficiently. Competitive pressure, cost challenges and increased customer expectations are increasingly driving organizations to improve the way they design, develop and introduce products to the market. To be competitive in the global market place, innovation driven organization need to deliver new products to the market quickly and cost effectively.

2.0 Problem Statement

Multinational Corporation (MNC's) is finding it challenging to have sustainability in their organizational system. Cost leadership and product differentiation plays a vital role in the organization system. (M.K Nandakumar, 2011) concluded that new firms which adopts cost leadership and product differentiation performs better than the firms which doesn't have a

strategic dominant orientation. New technologies and innovations should be introduced to the market fast before the competitors takes advantage and grab the market share. Introducing new products should be a vital strategy where most organization is lacking in this area. Top management too can provide positive influence in this area. (Andre A. de Waal, 2009) concluded that failure rates of the performance management implementation has decreased in the past decade and that the most severe problems organizations encounter are due to the lack of top management commitment.

Several factors pertaining to optimization and sustaining organizational performance has been identified in this study where each of the factors does influence in one way or another. Technology is being the vital factor in this generation where people are benchmarking products with the competitors based on the technological contribution level. Competitors are becoming more alert on the technological changes and taking prompt actions to be ahead and they continually request for quality improvement, rapid product delivery, competitive pricing, and other features that are best achieved in the complex

environments by the innovative organizational practices.

This study aims to identify among the factors introduced which include, Income, Technology, Organization Type, People and Quality which will optimize the organizational performance and to study whether is it from a single factor or from the combination of all factors introduced in this study.

3.0 Literature Review

This study examines the relevant characteristics of the factors introduced which contributes positively to the organizational performance.

3.1 Organizational Sustainable Performance

Organization should clearly understand the current situation of the market and take prompt action to enhance organizational sustainable performance. According to (Delaney, 1996), there are seven elements in the organization which contributes to the organizational performance which includes:

- 1) Product quality
- 2) Product innovation
- 3) Attraction of employees
- 4) Retention of employees
- 5) Total Customer satisfaction
- 6) Management and employee relation
- 7) Employee relations

Organization should clearly understand the current situation of the market and take prompt action to enhance organizational sustainable performance. (Gupta, 2008) concluded that the ultimate goal of an organization is to create an internal environment that supports customer needs and expectations and there are four factors which could lead to performance which includes cost, time, robustness and scope where cost and time refers whether the changes are introduces and implemented quickly at a reasonable cost and robustness where the change implemented in a manner that produces quality results without the need for constant attention and the scope indicates the magnitude of change that can be used to accommodate in the future. (Ho, 2008) defines organization performance as the indicator which measures how well an organization accomplishes its objectives.

Organizational culture should also be considered as well as it was argued that the organizational culture is a key foundation for the high performance work practices and could be a source of competitive advantage if it is properly nurtured. A high performance organization reports a clear direction (mission, vision and strategy) which shall be embraced by employees of all levels. (Applebaum, 2000) also argued that organization which maintains high achievement requires a positive workplace environment. It was argued that when a positive workplace is created, it will affect the employees' motivation to contribute more positively to the organizational performance. (Ogbonna, 2002) on the other hand concluded that some organizational culture leads to organizational performance and that happens when the culture is widely shared among all employees. Prior to previous studies suggest that a strong culture has a positive influence on organizational sustainable performance. Therefore optimisation of organizational sustainable performance refers to the strategies introduce by any organization to optimise its performance in terms of financial growth, employee retentions as well as product growth.

3.2 Income affecting organizational sustainable performance

(Dulebohn, 1999) introduced that the organization uses monetary plans to increase productivity, superior work force attitudes and better employees behaviours. (Atul Mitra, 2011) also concluded that job attitudes does corresponds to the relationship in income levels and it was also concluded that income has been a vital factor in motivating employees to work hard where it does influence the performance of an organization. (Heneman, 2000) also pointed out that positive influence of higher pay levels on employee job factors such as job satisfaction and full commitments from the employees. Studies carried out by (Carolyn Stringer, 2011) also concluded that the primary aim of incentives is to enhance the motivation factor by satisfying employees' needs through income factor. It was also argued that that relating incentives to performance actually motivates employees to increase their effort and performance.

Remuneration has always been the vital motivational factor in influencing organizational

performance and this is also supported by the studies carried out by (Doris Warneke, 2011) where it was concluded that considerations must be given to the total remuneration package for the recruitment retention, motivation and mobility of employee. It was also supported by (I.M. Jawahar, 2011) where he argues and concluded that even though the perception of fairness is important to all human resource decisions, it is also important to focus on the compensation decisions related to monetary factors. Employees who feel that they are less paid than others may have less respect for their job, less satisfied with their work and as a result influence the organizational sustainable performance. (Paul Theivananthampillai, 2011) concluded that pay satisfaction have a positive association with job satisfaction which leads to organizational sustainable performance.

3.3 Technology Affecting Organizational Sustainable Performance

Organization meeting the challenges of global competition and increased sustainability requires the achievement of excellence in innovation. Innovation can be a key driver for productivity, increased energy and material efficiency, improve performance of the goods and services as well as in the generation of new markets. (Gopalakrishnan, 2000) concluded that innovation have positive significance to the performance of an organization.

The increasing speed of innovation requires organizations in almost every industry to innovate as much as possible and to be fast in the innovation process life cycle. Speed in decision making enables organizations to mobilize against new opportunities in order to capture the market first and therefore Research and Development (R&D) can play an important role towards organizational performance. (Prajogo, 2006) also commented that there is a positive relationship between innovation and organization performance and advocated that a firm should develop or launch new products to perform better than competitors in respect to organization performance measured and it is also supported by the studies carried out by (Cozzarini, 2004) where it was argued and concluded that innovation organizations have higher performance than non-innovative firms. (Erdil, 2004) also concluded from his studies that organizations innovativeness

affects the firm's performance. Technology advancement is crucial in this demanding atmosphere. (Wolff, 2006) also concluded on the positive effect of product and process innovation as it opens SME's to new customers and markets. He also concluded that product innovation can provide more market share, growth and hence more sales growth.

3.4 Organization Type Affecting Organizational Sustainable Performance

Working condition in an organization plays an important role in motivating and inspiring employees to work comfortably and thus affecting organizational performance. It provides a culture which influence employees' commitment and performance by setting the practices and values for a positive and meaningful work environment and the challenge for organization is to create an environment where employees understand and commit to the organizations direction, strategy and goals.

(Md. Zabid Abdul Rashid, 1997) in his study also concluded the relationship between the corporate culture and work environment in Malaysian organization and found that there are significant difference between ethnic organization in the work values in terms of work commitment, loyalty, respect for hierarchy, harmony, preserving face and spirituality leading to employees retention in an organization and being fully committed towards the organization performance. It was also supported by (Cameron K., 1999) that organization performance is related to organization with strong culture with well integrated set of values, beliefs and the behaviours. That's because focused cultures provide better financial returns, which include higher return on investment (ROI), higher return on assets (ROA), and higher return on equity (ROE). (Applebaum, 2000) in his studies on organization declares that that high levels of performance requires a positive work place environment and practices that will develop employee's knowledge and ability to create value to the organization. It confirms that the high performance organizations work in three different ways which includes, creating human capital, creating positive organizational environment and creating organizational social capital. (Joseph T. Martelli, 2011) also concluded in his studies that

the organizational practices and culture does provide a positive influence towards sustaining organizational performance.

3.5 People affecting Organizational Sustainable Performance

According to (Muthuveloo, 2013) there are four main categories of people which could influence the organization well-being which includes Performers – Followers, people in this category follow orders and carry out the tasks assigned accordingly without questioning, they are normally non risk takers and possess low agility. Transactors – Reactors, people in this category are normally risk takers and possess high awareness with low agility. Loser – procrastinators, people in this category possess very low awareness and non risk takers (not suitable for an organization) and Transformers – Entrepreneurs, people in this category are visionaries with high awareness, high agility and risk takers. In order for any organization to make full use of the human capital, hiring the right type of people for the right kind of job is vital (Muthuveloo, Pulenthiran and Teoh, 2013). (Collins, 2006) also supported in his studies that human resource management practices are positively related to the organizations cooperation and organizational performance.

Every individual is unique and if their talents are tapped out appropriately could benefit the organization. According to (Jiménez-Jiménez, 2008), if the individuals are given proper trainings, they will demonstrate significant and positive effects on organizational performance. He also concluded that hiring the correct type of people in an organization is crucial and the knowledge sharing among employees is important and healthy for organization success. Employees who are in sync with the organization culture is more likely to be committed, perform better, stay longer, and promote the organization. It was also supported by the studies carried out by (Ho, 2008), where he discovered that self-development in people are vital in guiding high performance in organization. When these developments in people are carried out, it leads to increase in satisfaction, motivation and performance towards performance growth.

The organization should promote employee to participate in the decision making process which

in fact will exhibit the ability of the employees in their initiative to the day to day activities towards organization performance. (SANJEEVKUMAR, 2012) in his studies on the other hand examined the relationship between pay, a person's performance and concluded that when high performers are insufficiently rewarded, they are most likely to leave the organization to work elsewhere, this will impact the organizations performance where skilful employees will be leaving the organization.

According to (Taplin IM, 2003), there are various reasons why employees leave the organization which includes low level of wage as well as the organization's image and according to the study where employees perceived the level of their wage to be low rating and lack of future prospect, the employees are more likely to find their career elsewhere. Employees who possess personal identity orientation focuses on tangible benefits gained from participating in an exchange activity rather than the social rewards. Therefore relational trust strengthens the nature of mutual exchange and promotes employees emotional bonding which in return contributes positively towards organization performance.

3.6 Quality affecting Organizational Sustainable Performance

Customer satisfaction and cost reduction should be every organizations' goal. Some organization neglects the truth that the purpose of business is to create customers and it is in fact the customers who determine what a business is. Therefore satisfying customer needs are the priority goal of an organization. In an era of increased competition, the importance of achieving high levels of customer satisfaction has gained the attention of researchers. Organizations that understand customer requirements and manage the customer service quality will enjoy competitive advantage.

According to (Yang, 2004), one effective means of achieving competitive advantage involves superior service quality and the superior service quality measurably increases an organization's overall profitability (ROI). In order to capture the market and satisfy customers, it is important to have quality products and meeting the customer requirements is in fact one of the ultimate goals

for organizational performance success factor. It was also supported by the studies carried out by (Dean, 2004) that employee satisfaction, customer satisfaction and the organizational performance are inter related.

Quality management principles play an important role in the management of business operations and many large organizations have adopted Total Quality Management (TQM) practices in some form to improve the organization performance.

4.0 Methodology

To test the suggested model for this study, self-administered questionnaires were distributed to Multinational Corporations (MNCs) in Malaysia and the respondents are from different age, gender, education background and industry. Out of 150 questionnaires sent out, 127 questionnaires were returned, yielding a response rate of 84.6 percent.

Five point likert scale was used to measure the independent and dependent variables. The five point likert scale which was used in questionnaire will be 1 – (Strongly Disagree), 2 – (Disagree), 3 – (Neutral), 4 – (Agree) and 5 – (Strongly Agree).

4.1 Pilot Study

For this study, 25 questionnaires were sent out for pilot study. The reliability of the questionnaire was also assessed from the data collected through the pilot study.

4.2 Final Study

A total of 150 sets of questionnaires were distributed to respondents within Malaysia. Only 84.6 percent which is 127 sets of questionnaires were responded and returned to the researcher. There were no discarded questionnaires. Out of 150 questionnaires sent out, 23 respondents failed to submit the questionnaires to the researcher.

5.0 Findings and Analysis

5.1 Demographic analysis of the respondents

As for the demographic profile, the respondents were asked pertaining to their age, gender, social

status, income level, academic qualification, country of graduation, department, management level and job tenure.

5.1.1 Age of respondents

From the 127 respondents who participated in this survey, it shows that the largest group of 56.7 percent of the respondents were from the age group ranging from 25 – 35 years old. The second largest group of 21.3 percent of them were from the age group ranging from 35 – 45 years old then followed by 18.1 percent were from the age group less than 25 years old while 3.1 percent from the age group ranging from 45 – 55 years old and the least group of 0.8 percent were from the age group more than 55 years old.

5.1.2 Gender of respondents

Information on the respondent's gender was also gathered from the questionnaire. The number of the male respondents was 59.8 percent while female was 40.2 percent with the total of 76 respondents for male and 51 respondents for female. Based on the gathered information, the dominated gender among the respondents were males

5.1.3 Social status of the respondents

The study shows that 52.8 percent of the respondents were single while 47.2 percent of the respondents who participated in this survey were married. Difference in percentage between single and married respondents was 5.6 percent.

5.1.4 Income level of the respondents

The information gathered from the respondents displays that 54.3 percent of the respondents were from the income level less than Ringgit Malaysia (RM) 4000 while 35.4 percent of the respondents can be categorized in the income earning level of Ringgit Malaysia (RM) 4001 – Ringgit Malaysia (RM) 7000 and only 10.2 percent of the respondents were from the income level of Ringgit Malaysia (RM) 7001 – Ringgit Malaysia (RM) 10,000. So basically half of the population of the respondents who participated earns less than Ringgit Malaysia (RM) 4000.

5.1.5 Academic qualification of the respondents

The respondents were asked for their academic qualification level and the information shows that 72.4 percent were from the undergraduate degree level while 13.4 percent were from postgraduate masters or PhD level. 11.0 percent of the respondents were with diploma and 3.1 percent with certificate level. This indicates that most of the respondents were college and university graduates.

5.1.6 Country of graduation of the respondents

The information shows that 77.2 percent of the respondents graduated from Malaysia while 12.6 percent graduated from the universities from United Kingdom while 4.7 percent graduated from the universities from United States and only a small portion of 5.5 percent of the respondents graduated from universities in Asian country region. The information on the country of graduation may help in the analysis. This will help us understand the influence and exposure of students studying in a particular country towards decision making and critical thinking as well.

5.1.7 Working department of the respondents

The information gathered displays the influence of nature of work of the respondents towards the survey. From the five main departments involve, which includes Human Resources (HR), Engineering, Finance, Quality and others, the information gathered shows that the highest contributor to this survey was contributed from the manufacturing department which 30.7 percent of the respondents replied to this survey were from manufacturing department. The second highest contributor of respondents to this survey were from the quality department where 26.0 percent of the respondents replied to this survey

were from the quality department. The third largest contributor which contributed 22.0 percent of the total respondents were from the engineering department. The fourth largest contributor which contributed 15.0 percent was from the other departments such as the training department, logistics department, purchasing department etc. The fifth largest contributor to this survey which contributed 4.7 percent was from the Human Resource (HR) department while only 1.6 percent of respondents who took part in this survey were from the finance department.

5.1.8 Management level of the respondents

Likewise, the respondents were asked for their management level in their organization and the information pertaining to their level were gathered and displayed in table 4.9. It shows that 60.6 percent of the respondents who responded to this survey were from the Executive level while 22.8 percent were from the Lower management level. 16.5 percent of the respondents were from Middle management level. The survey indicates that most of the respondents were from the Executive level which is the level before they enter to the lower level of management.

5.1.9 Tenure of respondents in their organization

The information shows that 36.2 percent of the respondents attached with their company for less than 2 years, 21.3 percent of the respondents attached with their company for 2 – 5 years and 19.7 percent of the respondents attached with their company for 5 – 7 years. While 11.8 percent of the respondents attached with their company for more than 10 years and 11.0 percent of the respondents attached with their company for 7 – 10 years. The results indicate that majority of the respondents who responded to this survey only attached with their company for only less than 2 years. A summary of the respondents' demographic variables are displayed in Table 5.0

Table 5.0: Summary of respondents' demographic variables

Demographic Variables	Composition	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age	Less than 25 years	23	18.1
	between 25 – 35 years	72	56.7
	between 35 – 45 years	27	21.3
	between 45 - 55 years	4	3.1
	More than 55 years	1	0.8
Gender	Male	76	59.8
	Female	51	40.2
Social Status	Single	67	52.8
	Married	60	47.1
Income Level	Less than RM4000	69	54.3
	between RM4001-RM7000	45	35.4
	between RM7001- RM10000	13	10.2
Academic Qualification	Certificate	4	3.1
	Diploma	14	11.0
	Degree	92	72.4
	Master/PhD	17	13.4
Country of Graduation	Malaysia	98	77.2
	United Kingdom	16	12.6
	United States	6	4.7
	Asian	7	5.5
Working department	HR	6	4.7
	Manufacturing	39	30.7
	Engineering	28	22.0
	Finance	2	1.6
	Quality	33	26.0
	Others	19	15.0
Management Level	Lower Manager	29	22.8
	Middle Manager	21	16.5
	Executive	77	60.6
Tenure	Less than 2 years	46	36.2
	between 2 years-5 years	27	21.3
	between 5 years-7 years	25	19.7
	between 7 years-10 years	14	11.0
	more than 10 years	15	11.8

5.2 Factor Analysis

Factor analysis on the Independent Variables was carried out to verify on the

outcome on all the five Independent Variables which includes Income, Technology, Organization Type, People and Quality. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin

(KMO) measure of sampling adequacy was 0.748, which was above the recommended value of 0.5, and the Bartlett’s test of sphericity was also significant, 0.000. Even the communalities were all above 0.3 confirming that each item shared some common variance with other items. Given these indicators, all variables measures were retained.

5.3 Reliability Analysis

The Cronbach Alpha of reliability was used to measure the internal consistency of the scales. Reliability analysis was used to perform all the selected significant items within the factor. Reliability analysis allows the researcher to study the properties of measurement scales and the items that make them up. According to (Sekaran,2010) if the reliabilities are less than 0.60 then it is considered as poor whereas those falling in the range of 0.70 are considered acceptable while those reliabilities falling in the range of 0.80 are

considered good. if the reliabilities are less than 0.60 then it is considered as poor whereas those falling in the range of 0.70 are considered acceptable while those reliabilities falling in the range of 0.80 are considered good.

5.4 Pearson Correlation

Overall correlation statistics of the study variables displays that the Organizational Sustainable Performance has a significant positive correlation relationship with Organization Type ($r = 0.359, p < 0.01$). Income has a significant positive correlation relationship with Organization Type ($r = 0.555, p < 0.01$). Technology has a significant positive correlation with Organization Type ($r = 0.492, p < 0.01$). Organization Type has a significant positive correlation with People ($r = 0.662, p < 0.01$) and People has a significant positive correlation with Quality ($r = 0.491, p < 0.01$). Summary of the Pearson Correlation is displayed in Table 5.1

Table 5.1: Overall Pearson Correlation statistics of the study variables

Variables	Organizational Sustainable Performance	Income	Technology	Organization Type	People	Quality
Organizational Sustainable Performance	1.00					
Income	0.141	1.00				
Technology	0.344**	0.301**	1.00			
Organization Type	0.359**	0.555**	0.492**	1.00		
People	0.237**	0.429**	0.448**	0.662**	1.00	
Quality	0.260**	0.247**	0.471**	0.402**	0.491**	1.00

5.5 Regression Analysis

Multiple regression analysis was carried out to further examine whether there is a significant relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables. Basically it is to examine the relationship of the five independent variables which includes Income, Technology, Organization Type, People and Quality towards the dependent variable which is the Organizational Performance. A summary of the regression analysis is displayed in Table 5.2 where it displays that the Significant F Change value is 0.000 which concluded that the model is fit for the analysis.

The Multiple Regression Analysis showed a substantial correlation between the dependent variable – Organizational Sustainable Performance and the five independent variables – Income, Technology, Organization Type, People and Quality. The R² value indicates that the portion of the variance accounted for by the independent variables that is approximately 17.9 percent of the variance in the Organizational Performance is accounted for by Income, Technology,

Organization Type, People and Quality. The value indicates that those five factors explained Organizational Sustainable Performance by 17.9 percent.

The adjusted R² is considered an appropriate population estimator and useful when comparing the R² values between models with different number of independent variables. Table 4.5 displays that the adjusted R² value for this analysis is 0.145 which describes those 14.5 percent changes of dependent variable which is the Organizational Sustainable Performance can be explained by the five independent variables which are Income, Technology, Organization Type, People and Quality.

The results also shows that out of five independent variables only two of independent variables which is Technology (sig. = 0.048) and Organization Type (sig. = 0.011) are significantly correlated to Organizational Sustainable Performance. Whereas, Income, People and Quality are not significantly correlated to Organizational Sustainable Performance

Table 5.2: Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA)

Model – 1	Standardized Beta	t-value	p-value	VIF
Income	-0.089	-0.899	0.371	1.459
Technology*	0.202	1.998	0.048	1.506
Organization Type*	0.320	2.578	0.011	2.278
People	-0.074	-0.631	0.529	2.027
Quality	0.095	0.947	0.346	1.472
R ²	0.179			
Adjusted R ²	0.145			
Sig. F Change	0.000			
Durbin-Watson	1.927			

5.6 Hypotheses Testing

Hypotheses 1: Income has significant influence on Organizational Sustainable Performance

Referring to Table 4.5 which displays the summary of Multi Regression Analysis, Income is negatively correlated to Organization Performance ($\beta = -0.089, p > 0.05$). Therefore hypotheses 1 is not supported.

Hypotheses 2: Technology has significant influence on Organizational Sustainable Performance

Referring to Table 5.2 which displays the summary of Multi Regression Analysis, Technology is positively correlated to Organization Performance ($\beta = 0.202, p < 0.05$). Therefore hypotheses 2 is supported.

Hypotheses 3: Organization Type has significant influence on Organizational Sustainable Performance

Referring to Table 5.2 which displays the summary of Multi Regression Analysis, Organization Type is positively correlated

to Organization Performance ($\beta = 0.320, p < 0.01$). Therefore hypotheses 3 is supported.

Hypotheses 4: People has significant influence on Organizational Sustainable Performance

Referring to Table 5.2 which displays the summary of Multi Regression Analysis, People is negatively correlated to Organization Performance ($\beta = -0.074, p > 0.05$). Therefore hypotheses 4 is not supported.

Hypotheses 5: Quality has significant influence on Organizational Sustainable Performance

Referring to Table 5.2 which displays the summary of Multi Regression Analysis, Quality is positively correlated to Organization Performance but not significant ($\beta = 0.095, p > 0.05$). Therefore hypotheses 5 is not supported.

A summary on the Hypotheses tested is displayed in Table 5.3

Table 5.3: Summary of Hypotheses tested

Hypotheses		Results
H1	Income has significant influence on Organizational Sustainable Performance	Rejected
H2	Technology has significant influence on Organizational Sustainable Performance	Accepted
H3	Organization Type has significant influence on Organizational Sustainable Performance	Accepted
H4	People has significant influence on Organizational Sustainable Performance	Rejected
H5	Quality has significant influence on Organizational Sustainable Performance	Rejected

6.0 Conclusion

Of all the five factors introduced in this study, it is found that out of the five independent variables introduced, two variables were found to have a strong relationship with organizational

sustainable performance. The two variables which show positive relationship are Technology and Organization Type. Whereas the other three variables, Income, People and Quality which shows not significant. Final theoretical framework is displayed in Figure 6.0.

Figure 6.0: Final Theoretical Framework

Future research could utilize this model to carry out the research on other industries such as service orientated that includes the SME's. Therefore it is recommended for the future researcher to explore into other service sector such as banking, insurance. It is also recommended for the future researcher to include international elements (e.g culture, global issues and

etc) to make the research finding more comprehensive.

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